

Nigeria Energy Transition Plan: Pathways for Renewable Energy Sources Expansion

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Country's Context

- Nigeria's current population is 223.8 Million (UNFPA, 2023)
- Population rate is higher than electrification rate; Ratio 2.5 to 1.1
- Nigeria's electricity access rate is about 52% (According to UN Tracking SDG Goal 7 report for 2022)
- The identified hydroelectricity sites have an estimated capacity of about 14,250 MW
- Average electricity supply from the grid to household per day is 8-10 hours
- 86% of rural households in Nigeria depend on fuel wood as their source of energy
- In 2019 Nigeria had 22 million petrol generators (Dalberg, 2019)
- Nigerians spend \$12 billion each year on buying and operating small gasoline generators (Dalberg, 2019)

Context, Challenges, and Main Findings

- The absence of a tool for evaluating the current state of Nigeria's electricity supply and infrastructure has impeded the monitoring of progress in the Nigeria transition plan.

Aims:

- to investigate possible energy transition pathways that will provide valuable insights for strategic clean energy policies that both meet Nigeria's energy demand and cut emissions in the power sector.

Objectives:

- to identify and analyze strategic approaches that meet Nigeria's energy demand gap while simultaneously reducing greenhouse gas emissions; and
- to explore feasible clean transition pathways that align with sustainable development goals, in line with the available energy resources, transition plans and environmental considerations.

Research Questions

What are the pathways to achieving Nigeria's Energy Transition Plan? How do we reduce emissions to reach the net-zero target in the year 2060?

Energy Consumption by Economic Sector

Source: <http://www.nigerianmuse.com/20100221082947zg/nigeria-watch/historical-compendium-of-rulers-of-states-in-nigeria>

Nigeria's Current Energy Resources and Projected Energy Resources

Current Energy Resources

Scenarios

Using the OSeMOSYS Linear Programming Energy System Model the following scenarios were investigated:

Scenario Label	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions	Osemosys Scenarios			
BAU	No new investments in renewable power generation, electric stoves and heating, electric transport or energy efficiency are permitted.	Significant investment in renewable energy expansion will not happen without policy interventions and an evaluating tool/model.	Using Total Technology Upper Limit, BAU will remain the same without increase in the RE generation for the various technologies used in Nigeria.			
LC	Implementation of energy efficiency measures across all sectors to reduce the use of fossil fuel consumption and associated emissions.	Significant deployment of renewable energy sources, such as solar, wind, and hydropower, to replace fossil fuel-based power generation	Using Total Technology Annual Activity Lower Limit, we assume increase generation as follows:			
			Parameter	2023	2030	2060
			Hydro	20%	23%	25%
			Solar	0.3%	15%	23%
Expansion Future	Promoting and establishing clear and consistent policy frameworks that incentivize low-carbon investments and technologies to achieve net-zero in year 2060.	Significant robust policies and regulatory frameworks that promote renewable energy development would attract private sector investments, and create a favorable business environment.	Using Total Technology Annual Activity Lower Limit, we assume increase generation as follows:			
			Parameter	2023	2030	2060
			Hydro	20%	25%	30%
			Solar	0.3%	19%	30%
			Biomass	0%	4%	7%
			Wind	0.1	3%	7%

Projected Energy Mix/Power Generation

Scenario Summary & Findings

- BAU is not beneficial to achieving emission reduction.
- Least Cost and Expansion future will require significant investment to achieve the net-zero target
- While access to electricity remains a paramount objective, we must simultaneously work towards pathways that lead to net-zero emissions. This means prioritizing the expansion and deployment of cost-effective solar technologies.

Conclusion and Implications

Conclusions

- In conclusion, expanding renewable energy is not only an imperative but a tremendous opportunity for improving access rates and transforming our energy landscape. By prioritizing renewable energy expansion, we can achieve multiple benefits simultaneously. We can reduce our reliance on fossil fuels, increase access to electricity, and foster a more sustainable and resilient energy system..

Implications

RE integration expansion will also support business competitiveness in the nation and reduce the gap between supply and demand.

Policy Suggestions

Policy Insights

- The government should adopt and promote RE expansion best practices in the exploration and utilization of its energy resources in all sectors of the economy.
- Nigeria's policymakers need to mainstream and promote RE expansion to scale up the energy mix.

Future Work

- We employ the government and International Institutions to invest in RE pilot projects which would encourage private investors to invest in RE.
 - The Nigeria Sustainable Energy for All platform should be regularly updated to monitor and track progress.
 - The model is a work in progress and we believe that in future work we would take into account all parameters that may not enable the net-zero target.

Nigeria Reference Energy System

